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SpaceEdge: a service-based approach to onboard payload data processing and autonomous workflows

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INTRODUCTION

The current space mission scenario sees several initiatives aiming to demonstrate the new EO value chain, exploiting onboard data processing capabilities to enhance the information value, maximizing the exploitation of the available resources, both as communication bandwidth and time latency. These initiatives typically target the single components' advantages (e.g., an onboard computer, an HW accelerator, an AI algorithm, etc.), demonstrating the novel workflows they enable. Still, while each component has its own implementation, most of the system's components are common and do not need custom features.

SpaceEdgeTM is born from these considerations. Using the services implemented by the AI-eXpress (AIX in short) SW framework, it implements an AI-enabled computing infrastructure able to provide on-demand, in-orbit data processing resources. It enables the shift from "traditional" workflows starting from raw data in the Ground Segment, to the actionable knowledge-based workflow, in space. Such a framework is being developed in the frame of the AIX activity, co-financed by the European Space Agency Incubed program. The activity includes the onboard computing platform, the SW framework and their in-orbit demonstration on the first mission of the upcoming AIX constellation on the satellite equipped with a multispectral Earth Observation sensor.

FOSTERING A PARADIGM SHIFT

The space missions paradigm is constantly evolving. Nevertheless, especially in the EO market, the transition from a traditional service model into a commercial one is showing a few bottlenecks and barriers in specific applications, preventing new market opportunities from flourishing and limiting the effectiveness of the services delivered to the ground ([1]-[2]-[3]).

Some of the barriers are currently being addressed (e.g., launch availability & satellite deployment flexibility, versatile ground infrastructures, versatile software, relevant regulations, etc.). However, existing or incoming satellite operators and end-users of EO data are still experiencing severe inefficiencies, affecting traditional mission operational models:

1. missed information due to limited downloadable data from satellites (small satellites usually offer limited power, bandwidth, and controllability);
2. poor quality or irrelevant downlinked data,

3. missed observation opportunities due to limited onboard autonomy (data analysis is currently primarily executed on the ground);
4. delays in decision-making due to ground operator intervention;
5. late systems failures detection;
6. high complexity and flexibility of algorithms and science SW development and deployment.

These problems may be tackled today thanks to the increasing availability of onboard computing power and advanced techniques and algorithmic solutions, such as artificial intelligence, enabling autonomous operations. In particular, the advanced functionalities based on detection, extraction, and exploitation of data information content will be the core value points in this paradigm shift, moving the focus beyond “raw” data. These new functionalities will enable the management of significant raw data volumes thanks to structured and automated information refinement processes. They enable systems to react in near real-time to single pieces of information and to touch off new tasking for improved EO acquisitions specifically targeting the detected needs.

System specifications

Powered by AIX ([4]), SpaceEdge™ answers this user's needs by making satellite assets available as a service through DLT and allowing the execution of EO applications augmented with Trustworthy AI.

To this end, an experimental testbed is defined, targeting the evaluation of AI and blockchain-related state-of-art technologies and algorithms in the space environment, explicitly targeting items like reactivity, responsiveness, and latency with dedicated processing units (from RISC-V processors to VPU, TPUs, ...).

The testbed's main specifications are:

1. an orbiting platform, such as D-Orbit's ION Carrier [5], providing hosted payloads and ready-to-deploy CubeSats;
2. an SW framework infrastructure (implementing services and an abstraction layer towards sensors and onboard resources);
3. a catalog of onboard resources (HW/SW components and also complete CubeSats in standard configurations);
4. a catalog of processing functions and applications algorithms based on AI;
5. onboard service configuration;
6. CubeSats deployment on-demand;
7. support service to custom design needs;
8. Ground Segment support services for operations.

These system functional requirements have been derived from the high-level user requirements, and then the overall system composition has been defined at the components level.

System components

To provide services to end-users, the whole SpaceEdge™-enabled system has been modeled as a composition of three segments including:

1. a **Space segment**, constituted by two main functional (and physical) sub-systems on the ION carrier, the Platform (i.e., the ION carrier itself), and the hosted payloads (integrated by means of the SW framework);
 - a. The **hosted payloads** [5] are connected to the Carrier with standard interfaces already provided by ION's On-Board Data Handling sub-system (e.g., CAN, I2C, USART, USB), so there is no need to adopt ad-hoc solutions for the framework: the custom Mission Control Center already guarantees a full control;
 - b. The **ION Platform** is designed [5] with a modular architecture, suitable for easily expanding its functionalities. This characteristic allows for the integration of the HPC into the Carrier as a “hosted payload” and to serve the capabilities offered by the SW framework to all the other 3rd party “hosted payload” (clients) embarked (and to the Carrier itself whenever needed). The main functional modules exposed by ION are:
 - i. OBDH
 1. Routing and storage of data
 2. Platform/Payloads interface
 3. TM/TC
 - ii. AOCS
 1. Attitude control
 2. Environment sensing (Sun, Earth, Position, Time)
 3. maneuvers allowing pointing of the payloads
 - c. With its Services module, the SW framework per se manages the exchange of data between the HPC and the AIX-enabled client's Payloads and between Space and Ground Station segments. A basic list of functionalities belonging to this Carrier's subcomponent are:
 - i. Basic Payload data management
 - ii. access to platform auxiliary data
 - iii. time management
 - iv. execute ML/DL algorithms (inference)
 - v. library of deterministic functions

- vi. spatial filters, interpolators, spatial registration, features and novelties detection
 - vii. data-adaptive compression techniques
 - viii. the smart selection of data sub-sets
 - ix. TM packets formation functions
 - x. access to low-level processing resources through APIs provided by OS and/or BSP
2. a **Ground segment as a service** portal, devoted to operations;
 3. a **User segment**, constituted by a **user frontend** and a **service configuration backend**, shall be in charge of exposing/enabling customers to exploit a “configurable mission on-demand” in terms of:
 - a. starting from the user’s application;
 - b. selecting/ configuring sensors;
 - c. tasking acquisitions;
 - d. applying pre-processing;
 - e. selecting algorithms (eventually, configure AI\inference from pre-trained networks);
 - f. defining actionable information (to use or downlink).

The basic usage scenario is functionally sketched in the following Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Operational services flow

THE AIX SW FRAMEWORK

The framework, depicted in Fig.2, is composed of different layers. Each layer can use functionalities of the lower ones through a level of abstraction to improve reuse and safety.

It is composed of three different layers (four if we also consider the HW layer):

1. System Controller abstraction layer
 - a. In addition to the HW layer and its abstractions.
2. Monitoring & Control execution layer
3. Application Support layer

Fig. 2. AIX SW framework architectural schema.

Each layer implements its functionalities, including Image Processing functions, Supporting-AI functions, and a set of ready-made AI-based applications. Hereafter we describe core characteristics, features, and a few sub-components, for those layers.

System controller abstraction layer

A layer of abstraction is needed to de-couple the System Controller from the applications/services running on the application cores. This layer allows the management of communication between the two sides, in terms of RPC interfacing, authorization for the use of available RPCs and smart contracting that allows the negotiation and control of these authorizations. Applications and services executing on the platform application cores can use a smart contract runtime to autonomously negotiate the use of application cores resources and be granted the appropriate authorizations by a security-ring-based authorization engine.

Given the necessary authorizations, applications can use traded and agreed resources to perform tasks on sensed data coming from other connected payloads, receive commands, and downlink actionable information to the Ground. The communication links through the S/C platform to other payload sensors and the ground must be established using a remote interface client to the services through the System Controller abstraction interface.

Monitoring & Control layer

The Monitoring and Control services layer provides commanding, and observability capabilities for the different application support contexts of the SpaceEdge™ hosted payloads. A core executive subset provides an infrastructure of essential time, event reporting, publish and subscribe messaging, and data tables updating and verification services. These can be used directly by applications but are also used by the Data Handling (DH) foundation functions that provide Housekeeping, File, Memory, Network, FDIR, and TC/TM management services. Finally, an M & C orchestrator provides abstraction layers for the System Controller and for user applications/ services that need to interface to this execution layer.

cFS-augmented services

AIX services have been augmented with commanding and observability features for different application support contexts, using NASA’s open source cFS framework [6], integrated within the Monitoring & Control execution layer. cFS/ cFE services and custom applications build up the Core Executive, DH foundation, and Orchestrator components and allow the end-user to bring their services, combine them with existing ones and interconnect them through M&C services to create mission contexts. New services/ applications can be uploaded and dynamically plugged in a mission context and executed in isolation while getting access to the platform’s shared sensor resources through an interfacing System Controller module.

Fig. 3. cFS-augmented service/application support mission contexts

Those M&C services are moving in the direction of the Mission Operation Services [7] concept, by providing the basic MOS services functionality as described below, while targeting to gradually converge with the MOS standard services definitions in terms of:

1. **Actions** can be triggered by TC for execution and monitored via
 - HK telemetry data points limit checks
 - Execution counter values checks
 - Events emitted
2. **Parameters**

- status HK publishing via predefined parameters set
 - consumer applications/services register for those they are interested in
3. **Alerts**
 - via emitted Events
 4. **Check**
 - HK telemetry data points limit checks (periodic value checks and reporting)
 - Application emitted events monitoring
 5. **Statistics**
 - on checked parameter values (e.g., min, max, mean, std dev)

App-support services

The Applications' support services provide a set of functions to support applications at runtime. Applications which aim to provide deterministic and/or AI-based image processing or generic data processing services, can use services offered by this layer.

It is composed by a set of APIs, aimed at contextually 1) *de-coupling* the application code from the 3rd-party, and HW optimized, inference runtime, 2) *executing processing pipelines represented by user-defined graphs*¹. by which the user can (transparently) create a graph of operations and export it as a data file represented in a specific format and then deploy it onboard so that it can be executed by the Graph Engine, 3) *enabling the application to access acceleration devices* available onboard (e.g., GPUs, OpenCL-enabled devices, etc.) for off-loading parts of the algorithms to exploit parallelism.

AI-Augmentation services

Another distinctive feature of such a plugin-based architecture is the support, via a dedicated inference engine, of user-defined NN (and CNN) models via some of the most widely used and generic frameworks like Apache TVM [9], VectorBlox (OpenVino) [10], TensorFlow and the Open Neural Network eXchange (ONNX) format [8]. To this end, based on the actual HW availability and developing support, it is guaranteed:

- *Framework interoperability* -> Models can be trained using the preferred training framework and easily exported to ONNX format.
- *Inference acceleration* -> Easy access to hardware accelerators to improve inference speed
- *Quantization support* -> Different quantization techniques can be applied to get lightweight models

Next Fig.4 depicts such a mechanism, sketching the basic behavioral model supported and extensible via the framework.

Fig. 4. SpaceEdge™ support for neural networks: the inference engine perspective

This is meant to provide higher flexibility for the AI community, leveraging on the power of the cited frameworks to expose a minimum (and developing) set of standard ML operators covering tasks like:

- *Classification Tasks*
Analysis of the image (or tile) and discrimination of its appropriate type among the defined ones. Forest or agricultural field recognition tasks are part of this category, for example.
- *Segmentation Tasks*
Pixel-by-pixel image analysis that categorizes each of them accordingly to given classes. Cloud detection task is part of this category
- *Object Detection Tasks*
Image analysis to find instances of different object types, locate their position in the image, and classify them accordingly to given classes.

And such an element only depends on the development of the community around those frameworks as well as the adaptation of specific HW vendors for optimizing inference performances.

¹ In this context, a graph is conceived as a group of nodes, each representing a specific algorithm or function, interconnected by virtual signal lines

The devkit

As part of the User Segment, SpaceEdge™ also provides a feature based on the proprietary concept of the SpaceKit pluggable functions pattern. It allows composing workflows, made of C++11 source code function blocks, in a GUI-based application using graphs. This graphical design may replace the specific programmer skills and the boilerplate code for gluing together all the invocable components.

In order to test the expandability and thus reusability of such tools in a micro services-oriented backend ground, the following Fig.5 shows an example of deployment and enrichment of the Blueprint editor in a (C++) development environment based on Jupyter notebook for the creation of executable elements to be deployed in an embedded environment, e.g., RISC-V.

Fig. 5. Editor augmentation and deployment: an experiment with Jupyter and the RISC-V platform.

Customer-centered autonomous operations

SpaceEdge™ benefits from a strong synergic relationship with AIKO's orbital_Oliver on-board software library [12] for autonomous operations, as Oliver is one of the foundation elements of AIX.

orbital_Oliver is an on-board autonomy product developed with the intent of enabling some of the key on-board functionalities upon which the AIX framework is built: event detection and reasoning capabilities, and autonomous tasking.

These functionalities allow SpaceEdge™ to be operationally responsive to customer requests coming from ground, and to be aware of the operational context of the spacecraft in space, allowing AIX framework to take the most relevant and timely decisions to fulfil the user requests.

This approach enables the strong value proposition of ensuring the data acquired during the mission, as instructed by AIX framework, to be the most relevant for the user. High relevance of the data acquired during the mission translates to highly actionable and monetizable data being received on-ground, further strengthening the capabilities of the downstream services to provide the correct value to the user.

Example applications

The key capabilities unleashed by SpaceEdge™ consist in the possibility to disintermediate the use of space resources directly to value users. Specifically, adaptive use of on-board resources (for example for sensing payload nominal mode with low-power/low resolution mode and change of mode and use of resources only when specific targets of interests have been detected in real time from the raw/pre-processed on-board acquired data).

The following table sketches a non-exhaustive basket of potential applications across different market segments, as identified in the Copernicus Market Report 2019 [13]. The items in **bold** showed an immediate applicability in our Needs Analysis with users, and suite also to build common processing blocks for the SW infrastructure.

Market segments	Application Class A	Application Class B	Application Class C
<i>Agriculture</i>	Yield Mapping	Nutrient Management	Irrigation Management
<i>Forestry</i>	Forest Health Management	Forest Fire Monitoring	Forest Land Mapping
<i>Air Quality</i>	Urban Air Monitoring	Pollutant Tracking	Air Quality Analysis
<i>Maritime & Coastal</i>	Fishing Zone Surveillance	Algal Bloom Forecasting	Ocean Current Monitoring
<i>Oil&Gas</i>	Onshore & Offshore Oil Field Monitoring	Pipeline Monitoring	Gas Station Positioning
<i>Renewable Energy</i>	Site Selection	Energy Production Forecasting	Energy Production Forecasting
<i>Urban Monitoring</i>	Cadastre & Land Mapping	Monitoring Urban heat	Infrastructure Monitoring
<i>Natural Disasters</i>	Risk Forecasts for Hazards	Support early Warning and Response	Support to Insurance
<i>Security</i>	Land Border Surveillance	Vessel Detection & Identifications	Support to Search & Rescue Operations

Table 1. Intercepting application scenarios: a (non-exhaustive) traceability matrix.

Clusters of use cases have been used to identify the first set of building blocks that are common to several application scenarios. Possible short/mid and long term application scenarios comprise the following:

- Wide area monitoring for Wildfires early warning
- Global coverage for Oil Spill/Ballast discharge early warning
- Non – cooperative (with the AIS system) ships and floating objects detection
- Smart farming applications

Concluding, the SpaceEdge™ infrastructure enables applications aimed to the detection and the real-time reaction to events on-board, and to the monitoring of wide areas, optimizing latency and reaction times, or the resources usage optimization, based on actionable information content.

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